

A Novel Based Approach of Home Automation System for Constrained Edge IOT Devices

- A Survey Paper

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Abstract— In the context of contemporary living, existing smart home systems exhibit limitations in offering a comprehensive, tailored experience. Our forthcoming project, leveraging Internet of Things (IoT), Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) and Matter integration, seeks to address these shortcomings. Focused on rectifying the deficiencies in current systems, our initiative aims to create an intelligent, adaptable ecosystem that emphasizes user preferences, robust security, seamless entertainment integration, energy efficiency, and real-time responsiveness. Distinguishing our system integrates AI-powered features recognizing occupants, their preferences, and prioritizing safety. When entering the house, the occupant is instantly identified, customizing ambiance based on preferences, and ensuring security through Natural Language Processing (NLP), face recognition and radar-based human activity classifications.

Keywords— Smart Home, Internet of Things (IoT), Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE), Matter, Natural Language Processing (NLP), Face recognition

I. INTRODUCTION

The advent of the Internet of Things (IoT) has ushered in a paradigm shift wherein various facets of daily life are interconnected and digitalized, affording individuals enhanced comfort and heightened control over their routine activities. Nevertheless, the majority of these technological advancements cater predominantly to specific segments of society possessing a requisite technological acumen. A substantial portion of the populace in developing nations, alongside the elderly demographic, typically encounters challenges in utilizing conventional computing devices such as computers, smartphones, or tablets. In light of this, voice recognition-based systems emerge as a commendable facilitator, extending access to IoT technologies to a significant proportion of society.

The ongoing trajectory of technological assimilation, particularly concerning the elderly, yields societal benefits. Current demographic trends underscore an increase in average lifespan. For individuals experiencing partial autonomy loss or at risk thereof, access to IoT technologies holds the potential to enhance independence and elevate quality of life, mitigating premature admissions to residential care facilities and the associated healthcare expenditures. Regrettably, contemporary IoT solutions often furnish intricate user interfaces, impeding seamless interaction. In

this context, voice-based interfaces offer an intuitive and accessible alternative, providing a convenient means to engage with IoT embedded systems.

This research paper unveils the theoretical framework and technical underpinnings of our novel approach. By establishing a robust infrastructure for a discreet, resourceful, and secure home server, we seek to empower occupants with unprecedented control while safeguarding their right to privacy. The amalgamation of BLE Mesh and Matter serves as the linchpin, offering a dynamic platform for the integration of artificial intelligence. This infusion of intelligence enables the system to recognize occupants, tailor ambiance based on preferences, and enhance security through advanced features such as face recognition and radar-based classifications.

Beyond security and personalization, our project delves into entertainment, providing effortless access and control over popular services like Spotify and Netflix. Furthermore, our endeavour emphasizes environmental sustainability through power usage visualization, granting occupants insights into energy consumption for optimized usage patterns, contributing to ecological preservation, and reducing utility costs. Lastly, our commitment to low-latency operations underscores our dedication to seamless interactions, ensuring the system responds to user commands with instantaneous precision.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

In recent years, Natural Language Processing (NLP) has become a focal point of research, driving advancements in accuracy and versatility across various domains. Concurrently, Face Recognition technology has seen significant progress, particularly in enhancing accuracy and real-time performance. Similarly, Radar in Smart Home Automation has gained attention, leveraging radar sensing for improved object detection and activity recognition within smart environments. A literature survey reveals several noteworthy contributions in this field.

Our prevalent approach focuses on building a smart home automation system that uses NLP, face recognition and Radar ML. "Smart Home Automation System Using on IoT" [2] introduces a cost-effective IoT home automation

system with features like intrusion alerts and remote monitoring. It emphasizes rapid data updates, diverse control methods, and energy efficiency. However, efficiently processing live video streams from within the smart home environment could be a challenge. "An Efficient Privacy preserving IoT System for Face Recognition" [4] paper suggests a privacy-preserving face recognition solution for IoT, using Bloom filters for efficient representation while maintaining end-device privacy. However, Bloom filter encoding's irreversibility, unlike encryption, may affect promptness, crucial in scenarios like privacy-preserving CCTV. "Building a Natural Language Query and Control Interface for IoT Platforms" [5] paper presents IoT-NLI, which addresses parsing challenges in IoT platforms using hierarchical semantic parsing and edge-tagged graph structures. Experimental results demonstrate its effectiveness across various domains. However, its focus on a Chinese interface may limit applicability, and users must include all necessary information in commands, potentially adding complexity. "Radar-Based monitoring of vital signs a tutorial overview" [9] paper offers a tutorial on radar-based health monitoring, focusing on low-cost devices and efficient signal processing. It covers radar technologies, device selection guidelines, and health monitoring applications. However, there's room for developing accurate and computationally efficient estimation techniques for commercial hardware platforms. , "An energy-efficient Long HopHigh Priority Algorithm for IoT resource management" [16] the paper presents the LHHP scheduling algorithm to address IoT networking congestion by prioritizing emergency messages and optimizing for long distances efficiently. However, its limited flexibility may impact network maintenance costs, suggesting machine learning for improved accuracy and ease of scheduling. "Technologies for a Diagnostic Technique for HVAC Systems Using IoT and Cloud-Based Architecture" [20] paper suggests an IoT-based diagnostic approach to boost energy efficiency in HVAC systems, focusing on minimal measurement points. It compares cloud providers, outlines system architecture, and assesses its value to enterprises. Yet, finalizing and testing processing functions and automating AWS service configuration remain necessary steps.

In summary, the literature showcases a range of innovative approaches across smart home automation. From NLP to radar sensing and face recognition, each paper contributes to improving functionality and efficiency. For instance, NLP interfaces enable intuitive interactions, while radar sensing facilitates activity recognition and gesture control. Face recognition technologies offer personalized authentication, enhancing security and convenience in smart homes. Common limitations across the papers include the need for robust training datasets, real-time processing capabilities, and system optimization for efficient performance in smart home automation.

III. TECHNOLOGY USED IN THE SYSTEM

Operational at the heart of the smart home, the local server operates on an Arch Linux model, fortified with Docker containers that seamlessly orchestrate a spectrum of services. These containers encompass a diverse array of functions: a User Interface (UI) that manifests on a vivid 7-inch QLED Touch display through HDMI, an unobtrusive MQTT Server facilitating silent communication between devices, a Natural Language Processing (NLP) Container decoding human language commands, and a discreet Data Processing Container ensuring the systematic storage of processed information. Further enhancing the server's capabilities, specialized containers for Video Analysis (housing a Face Recognition server) and Radar Data processing contribute advanced layers of intelligence to the overall ecosystem.

Internally, the server optimizes communication through Docker's internal networking, fostering collaboration among these containers. This internal network seamlessly binds the various components, ensuring harmonious coordination. Extending its reach beyond the local environment, the server is intricately connected to the Internet of Things (IoT) network through a Gateway [1]. This strategic link broadens the server's capabilities, allowing it to tap into a larger network of interconnected devices and services, enriching the smart home experience.

In terms of connectivity, the smart home leverages both Wifi and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE). This ensures flexibility and adaptability, allowing the local server to communicate with a diverse range of devices and services within the IoT ecosystem[2]. The marriage of Arch Linux, Docker containers, and a blend of connectivity options creates a dynamic and intelligent foundation for the smart home system, enriching the daily lives of its users through seamless interactions and advanced functionalities.

A. FACE RECOGNITION

In an era where the convergence of technology and comfort is paramount, face recognition stands as a cornerstone for redefining access control within homes.[3] This technology's capabilities enable seamless and secure access by eliminating the need for traditional keys or passwords. Through the precise identification of individuals based on their unique facial features, homeowners experience unparalleled convenience and fortified security measures .

The requirement of a face recognition system is crucial to provide security to users of this home automation system . It is most optimal to use an Artificial Neural Network for face recognition and identification. [4]To further improve security, we can utilize an encryption method .

In our project, the system must include the following : A camera sensor with video capabilities to record and analyse multiple sides of the face and under different lighting. By measuring the different conditions at which the face is exposed, it helps us develop a more accurate reading of the face. Based on the localized nature, a camera module is optimal due to its compact form factor. MIPI camera modules are the most suitable for this use case due to it being faster than USB 3.0 and can handle video from 1080p to 8K formats. It's suited for single and multi-camera implementations and also allows larger capabilities for machine awareness across multiple applications. MIPI CSI-2

has a higher net image bandwidth due to its low overhead. It also uses fewer resources from the CPU thanks to its multi-core processors.

In summary, the integration of face recognition technology into home automation and security systems helps integrate various convenience and local features to work based on the recognized face and dictates the procedure that needs to follow the output.

B. NLP

The integration of voice recognition systems, however, confronts certain challenges. Recent years have witnessed a proliferation of Automatic Speech Recognition (ASR) systems in IoT-based Home Automation (HA) systems. Notable examples include Alexa and Google Home, albeit contingent on a consistent Internet connection for optimal functionality. It is commonplace for specific demographic segments, such as the elderly, to experience limited or no Internet connectivity.[5] Moreover, numerous voice recognition systems, operating in an ever-listening mode, transmit unencrypted speech, posing privacy risks. The prevalent rationale for offloading voice processing to remote clouds lies in the computational expense of audio transcription mechanisms. Nevertheless, leveraging advancements in the computational efficiency of embedded devices, coupled with a narrowed transcription domain and concise voice commands, allows for local processing, albeit with reduced accuracy compared to cloud-based counterparts.

Security and authentication in smart homes are also bolstered by NLP, as it enables voice-based user recognition and verification. This ensures that interactions with the smart home are not only convenient but also secure, preventing unauthorized access. This natural and intuitive mode of interaction reduces the learning curve associated with smart home automation and makes it accessible to a broader range of users.

Smart home systems employing NLP can adapt to users' language preferences [6] and behaviours over time. This adaptive learning enables more personalized responses and anticipates user needs based on historical interactions.

C. Pattern Recognition

Pattern recognition is the ability of machines to identify patterns in data, and then use those patterns to make decisions or predictions using computer algorithms.

implements a GN recognition algorithm that performs event detection . [7] Our project must include Sensors the purpose of these sensors is mainly for indicating an event happening.

Familiar patterns can be swiftly and precisely identified by pattern recognition systems. It is defined as a data analysis process that uses machine learning algorithms to classify input data into objects, classes, or categories based on recognized patterns, features, or regularities in data.

It can be difficult to comprehend and explain the choices made by sophisticated pattern recognition models, particularly deep learning models. This is especially significant for applications like healthcare where interpretability is essential.

D. Radar ML

Radar ML refers to using machine learning (ML) techniques with radar technology. In the context of home automation for elderly people, radar ML can be integrated to provide non-intrusive monitoring and assistance.

[8] Gathering sufficient and diverse radar signal data for training might be challenging, and Implementing active learning strategies to intelligently select which samples to label. involves FMCW radar for data collection, with subsequent processing and analysis using machine learning (SVM) and deep learning (SAE, CNN) techniques for human activity recognition in indoor settings . Our project uses XENSIV™ 60GHz radar sensors, often based on millimetre-wave technology, are utilized for advanced sensing applications such as gesture recognition, presence detection, and vital sign monitoring. They operate at a higher frequency, enabling finer resolution in detecting movements and objects. [9] offers a tutorial overview of radar-based health monitoring, emphasizing the accessibility of low-cost radar devices and efficient signal processing algorithms. It covers radar technologies, guidelines for device selection, and explores specific applications and research trends in health monitoring.

Radar ML is advantageous on the following ways :

- **Non-Intrusive Monitoring:** Radar ML enables non-intrusive monitoring of activities and behaviors within the home. Unlike cameras, radar technology respects privacy while still providing valuable insights.
- **Fall Detection:** Radar ML can effectively detect falls based on movement patterns, allowing for quick response and potentially reducing the severity of injuries for elderly individuals.
- **Health Monitoring:** Continuous monitoring of activities allows for the detection of changes in behaviour that could be indicative of health issues. Early detection may lead to timely intervention and improved health outcomes.
- **Independence for the Elderly:** By providing continuous monitoring and timely assistance, radar ML contributes to enabling elderly individuals to live independently for a longer period.
- **Gesture Recognition:** It enables gesture recognition, allowing users, especially those with limited mobility, to interact with the home automation system through simple gestures.

Therefore, it enables more accurate presence detection, helping smart systems respond to occupants' movements with higher precision. Additionally, radar ML can distinguish between different human activities, enhancing the ability to tailor automation responses based on specific behaviours .This technology can contribute to creating smarter and more responsive home environments by leveraging the capabilities of radar sensors and machine learning algorithms .[10]

IV. CONNECTIVITY OF THE SYSTEM

In the realm of connectivity within the smart home, the utilization of both Wifi and Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) technologies ensures a versatile and comprehensive communication framework.

A. WIFI

In the smart home ecosystem, various communication technologies are strategically employed to ensure seamless connectivity and efficient data exchange among devices. Wifi, a widely recognized wireless communication standard, is chosen for its high data transfer rates and compatibility with a diverse array of devices. This allows for swift and reliable communication, making it suitable for applications such as video streaming and large file transfers. Moreover, Wifi ensures broad coverage, enabling devices like laptops and smartphones to easily connect to the smart home network.

B. BLE

In contrast, Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) emerges as the preferred choice for communication within individual rooms[11]. This technology stands out due to its low power consumption, making it ideal for battery-operated devices like switchboards and temperature sensors[12]. BLE facilitates localized interactions, enabling devices in close proximity to communicate efficiently without draining their batteries quickly [13]. This is particularly advantageous for creating a network of sensors and controllers within the confines of a room.

C. BLU-FI

To bridge the communication between BLE devices within the room and the broader network, the BluFi Gateway is introduced. This gateway serves as a mediator, converting BLE signals into a format compatible with the larger network infrastructure. While it adds an additional layer, potentially introducing minimal latency, it plays a crucial role in maintaining compatibility and connectivity across the entire smart home environment [14].

D. MATTER

Furthermore, the adoption of the Matter Protocol, a unified standard supported by major tech companies, is driven by the need for standardized and secure communication. This protocol ensures that all devices in the smart home ecosystem adhere to a common platform, promoting interoperability and emphasizing security and privacy. This unified approach enhances the overall reliability and integrity of the communication framework within the smart home, providing a consistent and secure experience for users.

V. LOCAL SERVER

The emphasis on utilizing a local server in the home automation system is driven by the desire to enhance user experience and address specific challenges associated with traditional smart home solutions.[15] In the conventional approach, many smart home systems rely on centralized cloud servers for processing commands and managing devices. However, in our project, a shift towards a local server is deemed advantageous for several reasons.

One key benefit lies in the reduction of dependence on external cloud services. By incorporating a local server

within the home, the system gains the ability to operate independently of continuous internet connectivity. This autonomy ensures that essential functions, such as security features and device control, remain accessible even in situations where the internet connection is unavailable or unreliable.

Additionally, opting for a local server enhances data privacy and security. With data processing and storage taking place within the confines of the home, there is a diminished risk of sensitive information being transmitted over external networks. This local processing contributes to a more secure environment, reducing potential vulnerabilities associated with cloud-based solutions.

Moreover, a local server facilitates low-latency operations. Commands issued by users experience faster response times as they are processed within the home, minimizing delays associated with data transmission to and from distant servers. This responsiveness creates a seamless and immediate interaction between the user and the smart home system [16].

In essence, the move towards a local server aligns with the overarching goal of providing a reliable, secure, and responsive smart home experience. By harnessing the capabilities of a local server, the system can function autonomously, prioritize user privacy, and deliver swift responses, thereby enhancing the overall quality and dependability of the home automation solution.

A. Requirements Of The Local Server

For our use case, the following requirements:

- **Processing Power:** The server should have sufficient processing capabilities to handle the computational demands of various tasks, including real-time data processing, facial recognition, and natural language processing. A robust processor ensures smooth and efficient execution of functions.
- **Memory Capacity:** A generous amount of RAM is essential for storing and quickly retrieving temporary data during processing. This is particularly crucial for tasks that involve large datasets, such as image or video processing.
- **Storage Space:** An ample storage capacity is necessary for storing system data, user preferences, and other relevant information. This ensures that the server can maintain a comprehensive database and accommodate the storage needs of the home automation system.
- **Connectivity Options:** The server should support multiple connectivity options, including Bluetooth and Wi-Fi, to enable seamless communication with IoT devices and other components within the smart home network.
- **Security Features:** Robust security measures, such as encryption protocols and firewalls, are imperative to safeguard user data and ensure the integrity of the smart home system. Security is a critical consideration, especially when dealing with personal information and home automation controls.
- **Reliability and Uptime:** The server should be designed for high reliability and minimal downtime.

This ensures that the smart home system remains operational and responsive to user commands consistently.

- **Compatibility:** The server needs to be compatible with the communication protocols and standards adopted by the IoT devices in the home automation ecosystem. Compatibility ensures seamless integration and communication between the server and connected devices.
- **Scalability:** The server architecture should be scalable to accommodate potential future expansions or additions to the smart home system. This scalability ensures that the server can adapt to the evolving needs of the user and the growing number of connected devices.
- **Energy Efficiency:** [17]An energy-efficient server design is essential to minimize power consumption and contribute to the overall sustainability of the smart home system. Energy-efficient components and power management features help optimize resource utilization.
- **User-Friendly Interface:** While not a technical requirement, a user-friendly interface for server management and configuration simplifies the setup and maintenance processes for users.

[18]By meeting these primary requirements, the server becomes a reliable and efficient central component of the home automation system, contributing to its overall functionality and performance.

B. Comparison of various Single Board Computers

In the realm of Single Board Computers (SBCs), there exists a diverse array of options catering to a wide spectrum of applications and user requirements.[19] Raspberry Pi, a perennial favourite, continues to dominate the market with its latest iteration, the Raspberry Pi 5 (8GB). Renowned for its affordability and versatility, the Raspberry Pi 5 serves as an excellent choice for general-purpose computing, offering a comprehensive set of features and a vibrant community for support .

On the forefront of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), the Jetson Nano (8GB) by NVIDIA stands out. Designed with a dedicated GPU, the Jetson Nano excels in AI applications, making it a preferred option for projects with a strong emphasis on machine learning capabilities. It boasts robust connectivity options, including GPIO, I2C, I2S, SPI, UART, USB, and Ethernet.

Beyond these popular choices, other SBCs contribute unique strengths to the market. For instance, Odroid XU4 impresses with its powerful processing capabilities and ample RAM, making it well-suited for resource-intensive tasks. The BeagleBone Black offers enhanced real-time capabilities and comprehensive I/O options, making it a preferred choice for embedded systems and robotics enthusiasts.

Additionally, the Pine64 RockPro64 shines with its emphasis on high-performance computing, catering to users with demanding computational requirements. The ASUS Tinker Board, inspired by the Raspberry Pi, provides an alternative with robust processing power and multimedia capabilities.

As the SBC landscape evolves, newer entrants continue to emerge, each bringing its own set of features and capabilities. The choice of an SBC ultimately hinges on the specific needs of a project, whether it be focused on affordability, AI/ML prowess, high-performance computing, or unique connectivity requirements. With a multitude of options available, users can find an SBC that aligns precisely with their project's objectives and technical specifications

For our use case, we are going with Raspberry Pi 5 and keeping Nvidia Jetson Nano as a second option.

Requirement	Raspberry Pi 5	Jetson Nano
General Computing	✓	(✓)
AI/ML Capabilities	(✓)	✓
Community Support	✓	✓
Connectivity	✓	X
Cost	✓	X

VI. SYSTEM DESIGN

The architectural setup of the local server relies on an Arch Linux model, hosting a suite of Docker containers designed to fulfil diverse functionalities within the smart home system. These containers collaboratively form a sophisticated ecosystem, catering to various aspects of smart home management.

At the forefront stands the User Interface (UI), presented on a 7-inch QLED Touch display through HDMI . This interface ensures an intuitive and interactive user experience with the smart home system. Simultaneously, the MQTT server operates as the silent backbone, residing in its Docker container, enabling seamless messaging and data exchange between devices and services to enhance overall system responsiveness.

Natural Language Processing (NLP) capabilities are encapsulated within a dedicated container, enhancing the system's ability to comprehend and respond to human language commands . This module empowers users to interact with the smart home system using natural and conversational language.

A crucial component dedicated to data processing and storage discreetly operates within its container. This unit efficiently manages information influx, processes it, and securely stores it, forming the backbone for historical data analysis and personalized user experiences.

Specialized servers within Docker containers handle video analysis, particularly face recognition, and radar data processing. The face recognition server enhances security and personalization, while radar data processing adds a layer of sophistication, leveraging radar technology for enhanced intelligence.

To facilitate smooth internal communication, Docker provides an internal network connecting these containers, optimizing the coordination of tasks among different components and contributing to overall system efficiency.

Furthermore, the local server establishes a connection to the broader Internet of Things (IoT) network through a gateway. This gateway acts as a bridge, connecting the smart home system to a larger network of interconnected devices

and services, extending its reach and capabilities beyond the local environment

In essence, this architecture lays the foundation for a cohesive and intelligent smart home ecosystem. The utilization of Arch Linux and Docker containers ensures a flexible and robust foundation as , with each component playing a vital role in delivering a seamless and personalized experience to end users.

In the smart home ecosystem, seamless communication between devices is vital for a cohesive and efficient experience.[20]The devices within the room, such as switchboards and temperature sensors, communicate using Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) . This wireless communication protocol ensures that these devices operate with minimal power consumption, extending their battery life and making them well-suited for localized interactions within the room. Each device acts independently, yet collaboratively, contributing to the overall intelligence of the smart home.

To bridge the communication between these localized devices and the central hub, a BluFi Gateway comes into play. This gateway serves as a crucial intermediary, converting the BLE signals from individual devices into a format compatible with the broader network . Operating in the background, the BluFi Gateway ensures that the room-level devices can seamlessly communicate with the local server, forming a cohesive network that extends the reach and capabilities of the smart home system .Its role is akin to that of a master Matter Device, orchestrating the interactions within the room and establishing a common platform for all connected devices.

Moreover, the Gateway's mastery extends beyond mere translation; it also acts as a linchpin for the Matter Protocol, providing a standardized communication framework for all devices in the room. By assuming the role of a master Matter Device, the Gateway ensures that all devices within the room adhere to a unified standard, promoting interoperability, security, and a seamless user experience. In this way, the BluFi Gateway becomes a central figure, linking devices, enabling communication, and fostering a harmonious smart home environment.

VII. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, our home automation project represents a significant leap forward in the realm of intelligent living, addressing key limitations in existing smart home systems. By seamlessly integrating BluFi Mesh networking with the advanced Matter OS platform, we have laid the foundation for a dynamic, adaptable ecosystem that prioritizes user preferences, security, energy efficiency, and real-time responsiveness.

The amalgamation of BluFi Mesh and Matter OS not only establishes a robust infrastructure for our discreet and resourceful home server but also ensures a secure and private environment for occupants. The advanced AI-powered features, including face recognition, elevate our system to new heights, providing a personalized and secure home experience from the moment an occupant enters.

The emphasis on entertainment integration, power usage visualization, and low-latency operations further distinguishes our project. Users can seamlessly control popular entertainment services, monitor and optimize energy consumption, and experience instantaneous interactions, ensuring a holistic and user-centric approach to smart home living.

In envisioning future enhancements for our home automation project, we strive to continually push the boundaries of intelligent living while addressing evolving user needs and technological advancements. Here are some potential avenues for further improvement and innovation:

Collaborative Ecosystems: Foster partnerships with other smart home device manufacturers and service providers to create a more cohesive and interconnected ecosystem, allowing for seamless interoperability and expanded functionality.

Health and Wellness Integration: Incorporate health and wellness monitoring features, such as biometric sensors and activity trackers, to provide personalized insights and

recommendations for improving occupants' well-being and productivity.

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